

Effect of Integrating Periodic-Table-Software-Application on Achievement in Chemistry Concepts Among Secondary School Chemistry Students In Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to ascertain the effect of teaching the periodic table of elements with or without the periodic table application on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Chemistry in Ikom Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria. The sample consisted of 136 students selected by simple random sampling method. A 20 item 5 response objective test called Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was used for study. Face and content validity was performed for the instrument used in the study. Kuder Richardson formula 20 was used to calculate the reliability of CAT. Richardson formula 20 was used because items in CAT were dichotomously scored. The reliability index was 0.81. Two hypotheses guided the study. The pretest-posttest control group quasi experimental research design was adopted in the study. The treatment lasted for a period of two weeks. The data collected were analyzed using 2x2 analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The results indicated that a significant difference in the academic achievement of chemistry students when taught with and without the periodic table app. In conclusion, the study showed the importance and significant role played by instructional materials (the periodic table application) on students' achievement, especially in Chemistry. They have positive influence in achievement in Chemistry. Recommendations were made among them was, chemistry teachers should use the periodic table app to teach the periodic table of elements.

Keywords: Periodic table application, gender, achievement, student.

Introduction

Chemistry is the branch of science that deals with the properties, composition, structure of elements and compounds, how they change and the energy that is released or absorbed when they change. It is often called the “central science” because it combines with Physics, Mathematics, Biology and even Environmental sciences (American Chemical Society, 2020). The study of chemistry allowed scientists to craft stronger metals, brew potent rocket fuels, create new medicines and moreover introduction to modern science. It is a central science because it connects many other scientific disciplines. The foundation for much technological advancement that improves human lives are provided by chemistry. Chemistry is critical for developing, if there is the desire to produce the next generation of scientists and innovators that will acquire carriers in STEM fields and prepare students, chemistry as a subject of study is very crucial for the challenges of the future (Kirchhoff, 2017). Chemistry is the oracle and nucleus of modern science which ultimately is the foundation upon which technology is built. There are over one hundred elements (types of atoms) that combines to form all the materials in our world from the air we breathe, food productions, water purifications, drug productions, photosynthesis of plants, radiations, chemical engineering and manufacturing cosmetics and even biological molecules which cannot all be analyzed without chemistry. Chemistry is one of the science subjects that play a significant role in society. It prepares students for the real world of work through carrier opportunities such as chemical engineering, medicine, pharmacy, food science, and environmental studies (Mahdi, 2014).

The poor academic performance of students in chemistry has been a matter of concern to parents, government, teachers and researchers. Research have attributed the poor academic achievement of students to some factors such as the method of instruction employed by teachers (Adegbola & Depar, 2019). Pupils' perception of chemistry is in four dimensions (popularity and difficulty of chemistry, the relevance of chemistry, chemical aids and laboratory experiments, and future life and chemistry). Pupils have recognized the relevance of chemistry, but they did not perceive any connection between chemistry

and their future life can affect their academic achievement. Poor academic achievement in chemistry may be due to the dominance of conventional learning methods that do not utilize interesting learning media; thus, it might lead to negative views and attitudes of students toward science (Frailich et al 2007). In addition, a decrease in students' positive science attitudes may occur when learning is teacher-centered and there is a lack of use of ICT in science lessons.

In this 21st century proliferation of digital technology, any institutions that fail to incorporate ICT into educational system cannot seriously claim any success in getting its learners ready for life after school (Ogunlade, 2014; Nja & Okri ;2024). ICTs is made up of many components. One of the components is a mobile learning application, which attracts the attention of many researchers in the world. Thus, shifting teaching and learning process from traditional method of teaching to blended learning environment (Mehdipour & Zerehkafi 2013). Mobile learning-app in the educational sector is gaining ground. Mobile learning applications enables students to learn by themselves without restrictions of location, time, place and age. It encourages student-centered learning which in this case means that students do not necessarily have to attend classes before they can acquire knowledge (Khanghah and Halili, 2015).

Therefore, interactive learning media is needed to elevate students' attitudes toward chemistry. If these obstacles are not tackled, it thus affects active learning and teaching chemistry. It can be improved with the introduction of integrating interactive apps such as periodic table apps, chemistry lecture apps, chemistry quiz apps and chemistry dictionary apps into secondary school education which has become increasingly necessary (Irwant, et al., 2023). As per the American Chemical Society (ACS, 2020), there are various apps that can be used to help students learn chemistry from understanding the elements, molecules and atoms to understanding chemistry as a whole. This includes periodic table app, chemistry note app, chemistry quiz app and chemistry dictionary app which are only but a few.

This is a user-friendly app that contains a large amount of data on chemical elements for free. This app displays the entire periodic table sorted into its various categories which was endorsed by the international union for pure and applied chemistry (IUPAC). This app allows the user to easily find electrochemical series around the groups and periods also gives access to Wikipedia for further research, solubility tables and Mendeleev's periodic table format for modern education of chemistry (Torrens, 2021). It also helps the user access information on various elements like its atomic mass, electronegativity, density, oxidation states etc. and also visuals. The précised periodic table app used here is "Periodic Table Element 2024 designed by Digit Grove" (Izci et al.,2013). Hence, this study investigates the relationship between interactive apps and students' academic achievement mostly in chemistry in the university of Calabar science students.

Cognitive learning theory emphasizes that knowledge acquisition occurs through active engagement and problem-solving activities. Interactive apps can be viewed as tools that promote active learning by allowing students to apply their own thinking skills to meaningful tasks. These apps provide opportunities for students to engage with academic content in a dynamic and interactive manner, facilitating the integration and processing of new information. As students interact with these apps, they are exposed to complex situations that require critical thinking and problem-solving skills, thus contributing to their cognitive development. Teachers can leverage cognitive learning principles by incorporating interactive apps into the curriculum, providing students with opportunities to engage with academic content in a way that enhances their understanding and retention. By using interactive apps as part of their learning experience, students can develop the skills necessary to succeed academically and achieve higher levels of academic performance.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the 'Effect of integrating Periodic-Table-Software-Application on Achievement in Chemistry Concepts among secondary school chemistry students in Cross River State, Nigeria' specifically, this study seeks to:

1. Determine the mean academic achievement score between students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application and those taught using lecture teaching method in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State
2. Determine the mean academic achievement score between male and female students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State.

Research questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the mean academic achievement score between students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application and those taught using lecture teaching method in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State?

2. What is the mean academic achievement score between male and female students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State”

Research hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were formulated based on the research questions and were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application and those taught using lecture teaching method in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State”

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of male and female students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State

Interactive periodic table app is a learning application developed for better understanding of the pre-requisite concepts of atoms or elements, for learning of basic chemistry using mobile technologies to enhance students learning Apple, (2019). Periodic table app is a digital application, which is directed more towards learning general or inorganic chemistry and reinforcing various aspect of elemental periodicity. The periodic table has been studied for centuries and serves as the foundation for natural science and chemistry courses from high school to university. Because the periodic table is difficult to comprehend, scientists and educators have developed several innovations to aid in understanding and mastery (Traver *et al.*, 2021). Knowledge of the periodic table aids aspiring scientists in their ongoing learning and discovery of new elements through the application of known physical and chemical properties of previously discovered elements.

Several modalities, such as the popular CheMend game, mnemonic tools, songs, and cryptograms, have been developed to enhance the teaching of the elements and spark the discovery of new ones. For a long time, educators have been using traditional methods of teaching these concepts which ended up scaring more students that chemistry and the periodic table were very complex to be understood. While encouraging gamification when teaching periodic table learning, there is a need for balance between the fun and content meant to be delivered, without which students may not benefit from the game (Montejo -Bernardo & Fernández -González, 2021, Okri, et al., 2021 a). proved to motivate and support students in retrieving information but also has a great mastery of chemistry (Mokiwa, 2017; Tsai et al., 2020). The periodic table app engages the student to compete in the learning of chemical elements in chemistry lessons (Kara, 2019).

In agreement with the previous authors, Robinson (2019), ascertains that the use of Online periodic tables, periodic table apps (Ptable), and wallcharts have been supportive in promoting the teaching and learning of chemical elements, their trends and properties. Some researchers have used the method of transforming the classroom into a people periodic table by assigning students to represent an element of a particular group to engage students actively make learning interesting and improve their mastery of the periodic table concepts (Hofman & Hennessy, 2018). Izci *et al.* (2013) employed Periodic Table Live (PTL), an interactive online periodic table that is included with some worksheets, in their study to help students learn more about periodic trends. According to their research, students are more motivated to learn about periodic trends and are confronted with challenging thinking situations when PTL is utilized in conjunction with the proper teacher-prepared worksheets and questions. They recommended that teachers use worksheets to direct students’ exploration of the online periodic table and trends; to ask questions that encourage students to think critically rather than just reporting factual information; to require students to use graphs and charts to show how they predict periodic trends; and, after assigning worksheets to students, to encourage students to share what they have found with others.

Mobile learning applications were effective in increasing students’ motivation in studying chemistry There apps can be also integrated for searching chemical names or identifying chemical structures in chemistry lesson. Interactive apps like periodic table app, allows educators to teach without being restricted by time, place, enabling learning in or outside the classroom places where learning occurs naturally (Hang, et al., 2012). These interactive periodic table app allows most students to have grasping ideas of atoms or elements used in the general world from either combinations of these elements or in their pure form. Therefore, before teaching anything about chemistry, the teacher should determine whether the students has a firm background or knowledge about the elements in the periodic table, their individual characteristics and properties (American Chemical Society ASC, 2016), so it was suggested that most of this secondary schools focus more on the first 20 elements before advancing. Periodic table app makes the learning environment interactive. Interactive learning environment enhances students’ academic achievement (Okri et al., 2021b).

Methodology

The research design was pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental design with gender as a moderating variable. The study was carried out in Ikom Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. The sample consisted of

100 Senior School class two chemistry students from two schools during the 2024/2025 academic session Ikom Local Government Area, selected using the simple random sampling method. There were 136 students each in the experimental and control groups. The experimental group had 32 males and 31 females, while in the control there were 48 males and 25 females. The experimental groups were taught using periodic table APP while the control groups were taught using conventional teaching method. A 20-item five-response option objective test (Chemistry achievement test, CAT) developed by the researchers was used as the pretest-and posttest. The CAT items which were drawn to cover all the subtopics of the periodic table of elements on a well-planned test blue-print were rearranged with its options in pretest and posttest to have different numbering so as to give a vague impression that the tests were different. The reliability of CAT was estimated to be .81 using Kuder Richardson formula 20. Treatment lasted for a period of two weeks. The first author taught the experimental groups while the normal teachers taught the control groups. The data collected with CAT were analyzed using ANCOVA with pretest as covariate.

Results

Research question 1: What is the mean academic achievement score between students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application and those taught using lecture teaching method in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State? The research question was answered with the mean and standard deviation of the pretest and posttest academic achievement scores of the students in the two treatment groups. The results are shown in Table 1. As shown in Table 1 there is a difference in the mean gain scores of students in the two treatment groups. The mean gain score and hence the effect of periodic table-software-application is higher than that of Lecture method. This implies that periodic table-software-application is a better method of teaching chemistry than lecture method.

Table 1

Mean and standard deviation of the treatment groups

Treatment Group	Pre-test Mean	S	Post-test Mean	S	Gain score
Periodic table-software-application	15.075	3.391	41.21	4.1395	26.135
Lecture Method	14.425	4.258	31.085	17.6885	16.65

Research question 2: What is the mean academic achievement score between male and female students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State. The research question was answered with the mean and standard deviation of the pretest and posttest academic achievement scores of male and female students in the periodic table-software-application group. The results are shown in Table 2. The results in

Table 2 indicate that the mean gain scores of female students taught with periodic table-software-application have the highest gain score of 26.71 than the male students who had a mean gained score of 25.56. Apparently gender positively influences students' academic achievement when taught chemistry with periodic table-software-application.

Table 2

Mean and standard deviation of the academic achievement of male and female chemistry students in the periodic table-software-application group.

Treatment	Gender	Pretest Mean	S	Posttest Mean	S	Gain score
ChatGPT Assisted instruction	Male	15.44	3.618	41.00	4.150	25.56
	Female	14.71	3.164	41.42	4.129	26.71

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application and those taught using lecture teaching method in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State. The hypothesis was tested with one-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) statistic with pretest of academic achievement as covariate. The results are shown in Table 3. The results in Table 3 indicate that the calculated F value is 38.667 and is statistically significant at .05 significance level and (1, 133) degrees of freedom with a p-value of .000. That means there is a significant difference (p<.05) in the mean academic achievement of students taught with periodic table-software-application and lecture methods. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: Summary of one way analysis of covariance of effect of treatment on SS2 Chemistry students' academic achievement in the periodic table-software-application group and lecture method group.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	3870.860 ^a	2	1935.430	24.586	.000	.270	
Intercept	6789.803	1	6789.803	86.253	.000	.393	
Pretest	562.372	1	562.372	7.144	.008	.051	
Treatment	3043.861	1	3043.861	38.667*	.000	.225	
Error	10469.698	133	78.720				
Total	189590.000	136					
Corrected Total	14340.559	135					

*p < .05

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of male and female students exposed to periodic table of elements concepts using Periodic table-software-application in Ikom Educational zone of Cross River State.

As shown in Table 4, the calculated F value is 0.208 for gender in the periodic table-software-application group. This is not statistically significant at .05 level (p > .05). This implies that there is no significant difference in male and female students' academic achievement in chemistry when taught chemistry periodic table-software-application. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 4: Summary of one-way analysis of covariance of the effect of gender on SS2 Chemistry students' academic achievement in the periodic table-software-application group.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7.828 ^a	2	3.914	.226	.799	.007
Intercept	4723.845	1	4723.845	272.401	.000	.819
pretest	5.059	1	5.059	.292	.591	.005
gender	3.600	1	3.600	.208	.650	.003
Error	1040.489	97	17.341			
Total	108020.000	100				
Corrected Total	1048.317	99				

Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis sought to find out if there is no significant difference between the academic achievement of SS2 chemistry students taught the periodic table using the periodic app and those taught without the periodic application. The results showed that there is a significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of chemistry students taught the periodic table using the periodic application and those taught without the periodic application. The result may have been in favour of students who used the periodic application because the use of the periodic application in the learning process is highly innovative and motivates students to learn and therefore enhanced the understanding of the concept of the periodic table of elements. Another reason may be because students like technology and any method of teaching that is technologically based is highly welcome by students. This finding is supported by Torrens, (2021) who discovered that using the Periodic Table application of Elements improves students' academic performance as well as their understanding of chemical elements, properties, trends, electrons, and electronic configuration. This encourages students to learn other chemistry concepts that are related to chemical elements. It also agrees with those of Mokiwa (2017) who discovered that the use of The Periodic Table apps enables students to describe specific properties, characteristics, and constituent particles of chemical elements. They also recognize the significance of atoms and molecules and promote their understanding. The study by Astut et al., (2018) also collaborated with the present study reported that elements periodic table interactive multimedia was effective as a learning media, shown by large scale test results that 21 of 34 students had ≥ 75 score on the post test.

There is no significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of male and female SS2 chemistry students taught the periodic table using the periodic table app. The result implies that gender does not interact with treatment to affect student's academic achievement in chemistry. The periodic table app has been noted for its ability to enhance student engagement and make learning more accessible. This can potentially benefit students of all genders by providing personalized

learning experiences and immediate feedback, which may influence academic achievement positively. Nja, et al (2025) investigated the influence of gender on the academic achievement of students in a blended classroom. Findings reported that the achievement of students concerning the students' gender indicated an equilibrium resulting in a non-statistical gap between males and females. There was also a non-significant difference in examination grade between boys and girls in the study of Else-Quest et al., (2010). In a similar vein, Ajai and Imoko (2025) found that male and female students do not significantly differ in their academic achievement in mathematics.

Conclusion

The study showed the importance and significant role played by instructional materials (the periodic table app) on students' achievement, especially in Chemistry. They have positive influence in achievement in Chemistry. This explains why a subject like Chemistry will require real objects and interactive apps that can convert topics that seem imaginary to concrete for students' understanding. It allowed students to interact better in their lesson. It made students to use their intellectual ability during the learning and teaching process. It encouraged creativity, bringing learning homewards and at the comfort of their home and as fun and often improved and enhanced students' achievement.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

- 1). There is the need for teachers to be resourceful in instructional materials selection and utilization. Thus, regular training and retraining of teachers is hereby recommended.
- 2). Teachers should bring their teaching to the level of the students' aptitude by using familiar instructional resources and make classroom interactions more interesting so as to arouse the interest of the students and academic excellence.

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